

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AGHADIUNO****FIRST NAME: MABEL****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: MS Word 2019 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the correct way to write a journal entry in a reference list according to the notes-bibliography Turabian style?

Ionescu, Felicia. “Risky Human Capital and Alternative Bankruptcy Regimes for Student Loans.” *Journal of Human Capital* 5, no. 2 (Summer 2011): 153–206. <https://doi.org/10.1086/661744>.¹

Ionescu, F. (2011b). Risky Human Capital and Alternative Bankruptcy Regimes for Student Loans. *Journal of Human Capital*, 5(2), 153–206. <https://doi.org/10.1086/661744>

¹ Kate Turabian et al, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations – Chicago Style for Students and Researcher* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 192.

- Ionescu F. Risky Human Capital and Alternative Bankruptcy Regimes for Student Loans. *Journal of Human Capital*. 2011;5(2):153–206. <https://doi.org/10.1086/661744>. doi:10.1086/661744
- F. Ionescu, “Risky Human Capital and Alternative Bankruptcy Regimes for Student Loans,” *Journal of Human Capital*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 153–206, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.1086/661744.

2. What are the main elements of a research argument?

- Literature review, theoretical framework, methodology, and discussion.
- Literature review, evidence, data analysis, and conclusion.
- Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgement and response, warrant.**²
- Working hypothesis, claim, evidence, data analysis, discussion.

3. Looking for creative disagreement is important when writing a literature review. The statement, ‘Smith argues that the world population will rise, but it won’t’ is an illustration because

- This is an example of a contradiction of kind.
- This is an example of part-whole contradiction.
- This is an example of a contradiction of perspective.
- This is an example of a developmental or historical contradiction.**³

² Turabian et al., 2018, 58-62.

³ Turabian et al., 2018, 47.

4. It is essential to demonstrate evidence of construct validity when undertaking quantitative research. It is best defined as:

- Construct validity evidence is best defined as the evidence that the content of the measure is congruent with the conceptual or theoretical basis of the instrument, test, questionnaire, structured interview, semi-structured interview, focus group, journal, written, visual, auditory, or tactile exercise, or observation.
- Construct validity evidence is best described as the sum total of the evidence derived from factorial, convergent, divergent, and criterion validity studies.⁴**
- Construct validity evidence is best defined as the evidence that the total or content or factor-derived scale scores of the measure are not associated with measures of dissimilar constructs in a theoretically consistent direction.
- Construct validity evidence is best defined as evidence that the total, content, or factor-derived scale scores of the measure are associated with other measures of similar or somewhat similar constructs in a theoretically consistent direction.

5. It is important to demonstrate coherency in qualitative research. A description of coherency is:

- Coherency is concerned with the accumulation of evidence that the measures, the findings, and the discussion of the findings provide a relatively accurate answer to research questions posed in the dissertation while limiting other alternative explanations for the results.

⁴ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 40-41.

- Coherency involves accumulating evidence that questionnaire items, interview questions, focus group questions, and observation rating forms used in the dissertation are congruent with relevant elements of the available professional literature.
 - Coherency is concerned with accumulating evidence that multiple data sources and measures corroborate the dissertation research findings.⁵**
 - Coherency involves documenting evidence that other researchers involved in collecting data using interviews, focus groups, and observations have adequate training and experience to collect data that accurately reflects the perceptions or behaviour of the participants.
6. There are four classic limitations in a quantitative research study which it is good to address in a paper if applicable. These are:
- The four classic limitations of a research study are researcher, study participants, and treatment data analysis.
 - The four classic limitations of a research study are researcher, sampling, measuring, and data analysis.
 - The four classic limitations of a research study are sampling, measuring, treatment, and data analysis.⁶**

⁵ Sampson, 2017, 41.

⁶ Sampson, 2017, 59-60.

- The four classic limitations of a research study are sampling, study participants, treatment, and data analysis.
7. These statements regard the theoretical frameworks of quantitative or qualitative research. Which is the correct one?
- Adopting an emic point of view is the typical role of the researcher in quantitative research.
- The qualitative research paradigm is considered constructivist and involves critical theory and advocacy.⁷**
- Triangulation is a strategy characteristic of quantitative research.
- Qualitative research typically privileges one single methodological approach.
8. WHO house style uses English in its specific way. Only one of these statements is correct:
- WHO house style permits the use of either exclusively American or British English depending on the country of operation and the writer's preference.
- In WHO publications, the spelling of disease names and other medical terms generally follows North American rather than British usage.
- WHO publications prefer British rather than North American spelling.⁸**

⁷ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018), 137.

⁸ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: WHO, 2013), 12-13.

- Amphetamine, oestrogen, and aetiology are preferred spellings in WHO house style rather than *amfetamine*, *estrogen* and *etiology*.
9. Writers for WHO must use the correct terms and names. Which of these is the correct statement?
- The full name of Denmark as a Member State of WHO is Kingdom of Denmark.⁹**
- The full name of Sri Lanka as a WHO Member State is Republic of Sri Lanka.
- World Health Organisation and the WHO are accepted terms in speech and writing.
- Hong Kong has the status of a Member State.
10. The following statements address references and bibliographies in the house style of WHO. Only one of these statements is correct:
- In the bibliography, writers for WHO publications must give all items in English rather than the language of their publication.
- All legislation should be described according to WHO recognised convention.
- Writers for WHO publications can use either the Harvard or numerical system exclusively in a publication.¹⁰**

⁹ WHO, 2013, 61.

¹⁰ WHO, 2013, 36.

- The WHO convention for listing single-author entries with multiple publications in the same year is the author's Surname, Initial and publication date in parenthesis serially, e.g., Healy E (2011i) then Healy E (2011ii).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and Joseph Bizup. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, – Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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